

Mapping Research on the Ratio of Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budiarto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to determine research mapping around the ratio of Operational Costs to Operational Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Researchs. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the BOPO ratio; (2) mapping the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization results regarding the BOPO ratio based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the BOPO ratio using a Library Research study. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 736 journal publications regarding the BOPO ratio; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results around the BOPO ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 163 topic items; (3) based on Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 49 topics surrounding the influence of BOPO and 14 ratios topics surrounding the determinants of the BOPO ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the BOPO ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Operational Costs to Operating Income (BOPO); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Sharia and Conventional Banking.

I. Introduction

the Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) ratio in banking has grown rapidly in recent years, especially since the adoption of Basel II in 2004. Basel II is an international banking regulatory framework that aims to strengthen banking stability by encouraging better risk management practices. good and improve transparency and market discipline. One of the main components of Basel II is risk-based capital requirements, where a bank's capital requirements will depend on its credit, market and operational risk profile. Therefore, the use of the BOPO ratio becomes more important, because this ratio can provide a more accurate picture of a bank's operational efficiency. Initially, the BOPO ratio was only used as a performance measuring tool for large and medium banks. However, along with technological developments and information accessibility, the BOPO ratio can now be used by small and medium banks as well as investors who want to assess bank performance more effectively. (Nurcholidah, 2020) .

Initially, the BOPO ratio was only used as a performance measuring tool for large and medium banks. However, along with technological developments and information accessibility, the BOPO ratio can now be used by small and medium banks as well as investors who want to assess bank performance more effectively. In addition, banking regulations in many countries have also introduced minimum BOPO ratio requirements for supervised banks. The BOPO ratio can also be used as a planning and cost control tool for bank management. By knowing their BOPO ratio,

bank management can evaluate their cost efficiency and take action to improve that efficiency. For example, bank management may consider reducing their operational costs by optimizing the use of technology or improving their internal business processes. Currently, the BOPO ratio has also been used as a determining factor in credit decision making by banks. Banks tend to be more careful in providing credit to companies that have a high BOPO ratio, because they are considered to have a higher credit risk. On the other hand, companies with a low BOPO ratio are considered more reliable borrowers and have a better ability to repay loans (Aswan, 2019) .

Research on the BOPO ratio in banking has been carried out by many academics and practitioners throughout the world. Some of the latest research regarding BOPO in banking includes: first, testing the effect of the BOPO ratio on bank profitability in Taiwan. The research results show that the BOPO ratio has a significant negative influence on bank profitability in Taiwan (Sastradipraja, 2023) . Second, analysis of the BOPO ratio in banks listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. The research results show that the BOPO ratio has a significant negative influence on bank profitability in Indonesia and the BOPO ratio in Islamic banks is lower than in conventional banks, which shows that Islamic banks are more efficient in managing operational costs (Supeno, 2022) . Third, factors that influence the BOPO ratio at banks in Malaysia. The research results show that the level of liquidity and quality of bank assets has a significant positive influence on the BOPO ratio, while the level of bank credit growth has a significant negative influence on the BOPO ratio (Muhammad et al., 2021) . Fourth, analysis of the BOPO ratio at banks in the United States. The research results show that the BOPO ratio has a significant negative influence on bank profitability in the United States, and that banks with lower BOPO ratios tend to have higher profitability (Kusno et al., 2020) . Overall, the development of the use of the BOPO ratio in banking has helped improve operational efficiency and financial performance of banks. However, it is important to remember that the BOPO ratio should not be viewed as the only measure of a bank's financial performance and operational efficiency, because there are other factors that also need to be considered.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around BOPO in Sharia and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding BOPO. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research BOPO. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the BOPO ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

II. Literature Review

Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) is the ratio between operational costs incurred by the bank and operational income received from operational activities such as loan interest, deposit interest and commissions. BOPO is an important financial performance indicator to use in measuring the operational efficiency of a bank. The lower the BOPO ratio of a bank, the more efficient the bank is in managing its operational costs and the higher the profits generated from its operational activities. Conversely, the higher the BOPO ratio, the less efficient the bank is in managing its operational costs, and this can reduce the profits generated. BOPO can also be used to compare operational efficiency between different banks.

Banks with lower BOPO ratios tend to be more efficient than banks with higher BOPO ratios in terms of managing their operational costs. Good BOPO management is very important for banks to ensure business continuity and to meet the expectations of stakeholders such as shareholders, customers and regulators (Rajagukguk, 2022) .

Bibliometric studies constitute research method that uses quantitative data to analyze published literature, usually in the form of journal articles, books, or other publications. Bibliometric studies include quantitative measurements such as number of publications, frequency of citations, author collaborations, as well as network analysis and scientific visualization, to understand patterns and trends in knowledge production and scientific communication. Bibliometric studies can help in identifying trends in specific research, measure the influence of authors or journals, as well as help in identifying collaborations between authors or institutions. Bibliometric studies can also provide insight into how knowledge in a particular field has developed over time. Bibliometric studies are generally carried out using specialized bibliometric software that can automatically process and analyze data from academic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. Results from bibliometric studies can provide valuable insights for researchers, companies, and academic institutions in understanding trends in knowledge production and influence in the field (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is one of the software used in bibliometric studies. This software is used to visualize and analyze bibliometric data such as journals, articles, and citations related to a specific topic or field. VOSviewer can generate network and cluster maps from bibliometric data, and can be used to identify research trends, author collaborations, and most frequently occurring topics and concepts. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data from various sources such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. This software uses clustering and cluster analysis techniques to visualize the relationships between articles and research topics in the form of a network map that can be easily understood. Apart from that, VOSviewer can also be used to visualize data in the form of graphs, histograms and pie charts. In the academic field, VOSviewer is often used to perform bibliometric analysis to identify research trends and author collaborations in a particular field. This software can also assist in identifying the topics and concepts that appear most frequently in a particular study, as well as provide insight into how knowledge in a particular field has developed over time. (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Studies Library Research is a method or process carried out in research or academic studies to collect, evaluate, and synthesize information or knowledge that has been published in various sources such as books, scientific journals, conferences, and online sources related to certain topics or problems. Library Research studies are generally carried out to provide a better understanding of the topic being studied, look at the history and development of related research, evaluate the weaknesses and strengths of research methods that have been used, and identify gaps or opportunities for future research. In academic research, a Library Research study is usually used as part of an introductory chapter or Library Research, and is an important first step before research is carried out or the results are analyzed. (El-Halaby et al., 2021) .

III. Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Operational Costs to Operational Income (BOPO). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on BOPO in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish / Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Operating Costs to Operating Income " and " BOPO " throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding BOPO using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around BOPO using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around BOPO using a Library Research study (Rohimah et al., 2023)

IV. Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Publications regarding Operational Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Banking Sharia and Conventional

There are 736 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2009 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Journal publication data regarding BOPO by year					
Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	7	2014	30	2019	72
2010	2	2015	47	2020	89
2011	2	2016	69	2021	109
2012	15	2017	66	2022	131
2013	29	2018	51	2023	17

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Based on search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 3, consists of 42 topic items, namely: assets, operating expenses operational income, bei, operational costs to operational income, bopo, bpr, Indonesian stock exchange, capital adequacy ratio, car, deposit ratio, Indonesian securities, equity, ldr, loan, net interest margin, nim, non performing loan, npl, npl bopo, npl, ldr, npl nim, financial services authority, operating income, influence of capital adequacy, influence of car, influence of loan, performing loan, company, company, profitability, purposive sampling, return, roa, roe, significant to profitability, significant to roa, spss, tbk, analysis techniques, f test, t test.
- Cluster 4, consists of 7 topic items, namely: car influence analysis, hypothesis, multiple regression analysis, regression model, research model, variable capital adequacy ratio, variable car.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Effect of Operational Costs on Operational Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 49 effects of BOPO on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Audit Opinion. A high BOPO can cause auditors to provide an unfavorable opinion on the bank's financial statements. This can happen because high BOPO can reduce the bank's financial performance and thus affect the quality of the bank's financial reports.

(2) Wadiah savings bonus. A high BOPO can affect the Wadiah savings bonus given by the bank. This happens because high BOPO can reduce bank profits so that banks can reduce the amount of bonuses given to customers.

(3) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. An increase in BOPO can have a negative impact on CAR. If BOPO increases, then the operational costs that banks must pay will also increase. If it is not balanced with an increase in operating income, banks could experience pressure on their capital, which in turn could have an impact on CAR. A decrease in BOPO can have a positive impact on CAR. If BOPO decreases, banking operational costs will decrease, so that banks have more resources to strengthen their capital. This can increase banking CAR.

(4) Debt to Asset Ratio /DAR. An increase in BOPO can have a negative impact on DAR. If BOPO increases, then the operational costs that banks must pay will also increase. If it is not balanced with an increase in operating income, banks could experience pressure on their debt management, which in turn could have an impact on DAR. A decrease in BOPO can have a positive impact on DAR. If BOPO decreases, banking operational costs will decrease, so that banks have more resources to finance their assets. This can increase banking DAR.

(5) Fee Based Income. An increase in BOPO can have a negative impact on Fee Based Income. If banking operational costs increase, banks may not be able to develop or promote more or better banking services. This can reduce banking Fee Based Income. A decrease in BOPO can have a positive impact on Fee Based Income. If banking operational costs fall, banks can develop more banking services and promote new products that can increase banking Fee Based Income.

(6) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. The higher the BOPO of a bank, the higher the operational costs that the bank must bear. This can reduce the bank's ability to provide new loans to customers or increase deposit interest rates to attract funds from customers. In this case, a high BOPO can affect the FDR to be low.

(7) Financial Distress. A high BOPO can be a financial indicator distress or financial difficulties for the bank. This can occur when the bank's operational costs are higher than operating income, which can reduce bank profits or even cause

losses. In addition, high BOPO can affect a bank's financial performance which can impact the bank's reputation and customer trust.

(8) Stock price. High BOPO can also affect bank share prices. If a bank's BOPO continues to increase and causes a decline in the bank's financial performance, investors may become less interested in buying shares in the bank. This can cause a decline in bank share prices in the market.

(9) Capital adequacy. In the long term, high BOPO can have an impact on bank capital adequacy. This is because banks that have high BOPO tend to have lower profits. Low profits can affect bank capital adequacy because these profits are usually used to strengthen bank capital. In turn, low capital adequacy can affect a bank's financial health and hinder the bank's ability to provide credit and other financial services to the public. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to BOPO and optimize operational costs in order to maintain healthy capital adequacy.

(10) Zakat compliance. A high BOPO ratio can affect banking zakat compliance because large operational costs can reduce the amount of zakat that can be paid by the bank. In this case, banking zakat compliance may decrease because high operational costs can reduce the bank's ability to fulfill its obligation to pay zakat.

(11) Problematic credit. An increase in BOPO can cause credit problems for banks. This is because the higher the bank's operational costs, the greater the pressure the bank will feel in seeking income. One way banks seek income is by providing credit. However, if the bank gives credit to parties who are unable to pay it back, then credit problems will arise. When a bank's BOPO is high, the bank may tighten credit requirements to avoid the risk of non-performing loans. However, these actions can affect consumer purchasing power and slow economic growth. On the other hand, if banks make credit requirements easier to generate income, the risk of non-performing loans can increase.

(12) Credit quality. A high BOPO ratio can affect the quality of banking credit because large operational costs can reduce the bank's ability to carry out credit supervision effectively. In this case, the quality of banking credit can decline because high operational costs can reduce the bank's ability to carry out intensive credit monitoring and provide quality services and products.

(13) Net profit. A high BOPO ratio can affect a bank's net profit because large operational costs can eat up a large portion of operational income, thereby reducing the profits generated. In this case, banking net profits can decrease because high operational costs can reduce the profits generated.

(14) Operating profit. A high BOPO ratio can affect banking operating profits because large operational costs can reduce the profit margin generated from operational activities. This can reduce bank operating profits. Conversely, a low BOPO ratio can increase bank operating profits.

(15) Liquidity. A high BOPO ratio can affect banking liquidity because high operational costs can reduce the funds available to be invested or used to meet short-term obligations. This can reduce the level of banking liquidity. On the other hand, a low BOPO ratio can increase banking liquidity.

(16) Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR. A high BOPO ratio can affect banking LDR because high operational costs can affect the bank's ability to attract funds from customers. This can affect the banking LDR ratio because banks may not have enough funds to provide credit. On the other hand, a low BOPO ratio can increase banking LDR because banks have more funds to provide as credit.

(17) Level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits. BOPO can affect the level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits because the lower the BOPO, the greater the bank's possibility of providing better profit sharing for customers who choose Mudharabah deposit products. This can increase customer confidence and increase the amount of funds received by the bank through Mudharabah deposits.

(18) Total assets. BOPO can affect a bank's total assets because the higher the BOPO, the greater the operational costs that the bank must bear. This can reduce bank profits and reduce the bank's ability to make larger investments. Conversely, the lower the BOPO, the higher the bank's possibility of increasing total assets through greater profits and the ability to make larger investments.

(19) Allowance for Impairment Losses/CKPN. An increase in BOPO followed by a decrease in operational income can affect the amount of CKPN. This is because when BOPO increases, it means that operational costs that must be incurred by banks also increase. If this is followed by a decline in operating income, banks may experience difficulty in forming sufficient CKPN to anticipate existing credit risks. An increase in BOPO followed by an increase in operational income can have a positive impact on the size of CKPN. This is because banks have sufficient sources of income to form sufficient CKPN to anticipate existing credit risks.

(20) Murabahah Margin. A high BOPO ratio can reduce banking murabahah margins because large operational costs can eat up part of operational income. In this case, low murabahah margins can affect banking profitability in the sharia financing segment.

(21) Market Share. A high BOPO ratio can affect banking market share because large operational costs can affect a bank's ability to compete with other banks in the market. In this case, banking market share may decrease because high operational costs can reduce the bank's ability to offer products and services at more competitive prices.

(22) Net Interest Margin /NIM. A high BOPO ratio can affect a bank's NIM because large operational costs can eat up a large portion of operating income, thereby reducing interest margins. In this case, banking NIM may decrease because high operational costs can reduce interest profits generated from deposits and financing.

(23) Net Profit Margin /NPM. High BOPO can affect a bank's NPM. This happens because high BOPO can reduce the bank's net profit so that the bank's NPM can decrease.

(24) Net Operating Margin /NOM. The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's NOM, because higher operational costs will reduce the bank's operational profits. Therefore, a high BOPO can have a negative impact on a bank's financial performance.

(25) Non Performing Loans /NPL. High BOPO can worsen a bank's NPL, because higher operational costs can affect the bank's ability to settle maturing loans. This can trigger increased credit risk and potential losses for banks.

(26) Non Performing Financing /NPF. The effect of BOPO on the NPF of Islamic banks is the same as the effect of BOPO on the NPL of conventional banks. The higher the BOPO, the greater the possibility that Islamic banks will face credit risks and greater financial losses due to unpaid financing.

(27) Company value. High BOPO can reduce company value because high operational costs can reduce bank revenues and profits. On the other hand, a low BOPO can increase company value because the bank can maximize its income with lower operational costs.

(28) Return on assets. Low BOPO can increase return on assets because banks can allocate resources more effectively. On the other hand, high BOPO can reduce return on assets because high operational costs can reduce bank revenues and profits.

(29) Bank profit growth. Low BOPO can increase bank profit growth because banks can maximize their income with lower operational costs. On the other hand, high BOPO can reduce bank profit growth because high operational costs can reduce bank revenue and profits.

(30) Changes in bank profits. The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's operational efficiency and the greater the operational costs that must be borne. This can cause a decrease in bank profits because banks have to cut profits to cover high operational costs.

(31) Providing credit. The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's ability to provide credit because the bank has to bear higher operational costs. If the bank is unable to provide credit, then the bank cannot generate interest income which can reduce the bank's overall income.

(32) Credit distribution. The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's ability to distribute credit. Banks may not have sufficient funds to distribute credit because they have to bear higher operational costs. As a result, banks may experience a decline in credit growth and interest income which can affect overall bank income.

(33) Credit growth. High credit growth tends to increase bank operating income. In this case, if the BOPO is high, this indicates that the bank's operational costs are relatively higher compared to its income, which can reduce the bank's profitability.

(34) Asset growth. High asset growth can increase bank operational income through interest and fees obtained from bank operational activities. However, if BOPO is high, this indicates that the bank is having difficulty managing its operational costs, which can reduce the bank's profitability.

(35) Ijarah Financing. If a bank has a high level of Ijarah financing, this can increase the bank's operational income. However, if BOPO is high, this indicates that the bank's operational costs are relatively higher compared to its operating income, which can reduce the bank's profitability.

(36) Mudharabah Financing. If a bank has a high level of Mudharabah financing, this can increase the bank's operational income. However, if BOPO is high, this indicates that the bank's operational costs are relatively higher compared to its operating income, which can reduce the bank's profitability.

(37) Price Earning Ratio /PER. If a bank's PER is high, this shows that investors believe that the bank's profit prospects are good in the future. However, if BOPO is high, this can reduce profits per share and as a result reduce the PER value of the bank's shares.

(38) Profit Distribution Management. If a bank is able to manage its BOPO well, the bank can increase its net profit, thereby increasing dividend distribution and the bank's overall financial performance. However, if BOPO is high, the bank's net profit can decrease and reduce the bank's ability to distribute dividends.

(39) Bank ratings. The lower the BOPO, the better the bank's operational performance and the higher the likelihood that the bank will obtain a better rating. A better rating can strengthen customer and investor confidence in the bank, thereby increasing bank liquidity.

(40) Bond rating. The lower the BOPO, the better the bank's operational performance and the higher the likelihood that the bank will obtain a better rating. A better rating can increase investor confidence in bank bonds and strengthen the bank's position in the capital market.

(41) Murabahah financing risks. If a bank has a high level of Murabahah financing, this can increase the bank's operational income. However, if BOPO is high, this indicates that the bank's operational costs are relatively higher compared to its operating income, which can reduce bank profitability and increase the risk of Murabahah financing.

(42) Return On Assets /ROA. The lower the BOPO, the better the bank's operational performance and the higher the possibility that the bank will obtain a better ROA. A high ROA shows that the bank is able to generate greater profits from the assets it owns, thereby strengthening the bank's financial performance.

(43) Return On Equity /ROE. The lower the BOPO, the better the bank's operational performance and the higher the possibility that the bank will obtain a better ROE. A high ROE shows that the bank is able to generate greater profits from the capital it has, thereby strengthening the bank's position in the capital market.

(44) Stock returns. The lower the BOPO, the better the bank's operational performance and the higher the possibility that investors will get better stock returns. High stock returns indicate that the bank is able to generate large profits and provide added value for shareholders.

(45) Bank profitability. BOPO affects bank profitability because the higher the BOPO, the greater the operational costs that the bank must bear. This can reduce bank profits and affect the bank's profitability level. On the other hand, the lower the BOPO, the smaller the operational costs that the bank must bear, so that it can increase the bank's profits and profitability.

(46) Risk of bank bankruptcy. The higher the BOPO, the greater the risk of bank bankruptcy because high operational costs can reduce profits and the bank's ability to pay existing obligations. However, the risk of bank bankruptcy can also be managed through effective risk management and appropriate investment policies.

(47) Mudharabah Savings. BOPO can affect Mudharabah savings because the lower the BOPO, the higher the bank's possibility of providing better profits for customers who choose Mudharabah products. This can increase customer confidence and increase the amount of Mudharabah deposits received by the bank.

(48) Bank financial stability. BOPO can affect a bank's financial stability because the higher the BOPO, the greater the risk of bank bankruptcy and the lower the bank's ability to fulfill financial obligations. This could threaten the bank's financial stability. Conversely, the lower the BOPO, the higher the bank's financial stability because the bank has a better ability to manage risks and fulfill financial obligations.

(49) Tax Avoidance. BOPO can also influence the level of tax avoidance because the higher the BOPO, the greater the opportunity for banks to carry out tax avoidance by delaying tax payments or using different company layers to reduce tax liabilities. This can reduce state tax revenues and can affect bank credibility.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Determinant Variables of Operational Costs on Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 14 determinant variables for BOPO in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Productive assets. The greater the number of productive assets a bank has, the greater the potential operational income that can be generated. If a bank can utilize its productive assets well, BOPO tends to decrease because greater operating income can cover the operational costs incurred.

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear risk, thereby reducing costs associated with risk. On the other hand, if CAR is low, then banks have to pay more fees to reduce risk, which can cause BOPO to rise.

(3) Third Party Funds/DPK. The higher the TPF, the more sources of funds the bank can utilize for its operational activities. This can reduce operational costs because banks do not need to pay higher interest to collect funds from other parties. Thus, BOPO tends to decrease if DPK is higher.

(4) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. The higher the FDR, the greater the risk the bank faces because they issue more loans compared to the amount of funds received. If the FDR is high, the bank must pay higher interest to collect funds from other parties, which can increase operational costs and affect BOPO.

(5) Inflation. Inflation can affect bank operational costs and non-performing loans. If inflation is high, bank operational costs will increase because the prices of goods and services used by banks for operations also increase. Apart from that, inflation can also affect non-performing loans because customers' ability to pay debts is also affected by inflation. If non-performing loans increase, the bank will have to bear higher costs to settle the debt, which can affect BOPO.

(6) Problematic credit. Problematic credit can affect BOPO because the bank has to bear higher costs to resolve the debt, such as legal consultation fees or court costs. Apart from that, non-performing loans can also affect the bank's reputation and reduce customer trust, which can reduce the amount of funds the bank receives from customers and affect BOPO.

(7) Exchange rates/currency rates. The exchange rate/currency exchange rate can affect BOPO because it can affect bank operational costs, bank operating income, and non-performing loan costs. If the exchange rate/currency exchange rate experiences significant fluctuations, the bank must bear higher costs to balance the effect of these fluctuations. In addition, if the exchange rate/currency exchange rate decreases, banks that have assets in foreign currency will experience a decrease in asset value and reduce their operating income. In addition, if customers who have debts in foreign currency have difficulty paying their debts due to unfavorable currency exchange rates, then the bank must bear higher costs of non-performing loans.

(8) Liquidity. Liquidity can affect BOPO because it can affect bank operational costs and bank operational income. If a bank experiences liquidity problems, the bank must pay higher interest to borrow funds from other parties, which can increase operational costs and affect BOPO. In addition, if the bank does not have sufficient liquidity, the bank cannot utilize the funds it has to generate sufficient operating income, which can also affect BOPO.

(9) Non Performing Financing /NPF. NPF can affect BOPO because it can affect bank operational costs, bank operating income and non-performing loan costs. If the NPF amount increases, the bank must bear higher costs to settle the debt, such as legal consultation fees or court costs. Apart from that, NPF can also affect the bank's reputation and reduce customer trust, which can reduce the amount of funds the bank receives from customers and affect BOPO.

(10) Non Performing Loans /NPL. NPL can affect BOPO in banking because it can affect bank operational costs, bank operating income and non-performing loan costs. If the number of NPLs increases, the bank must bear higher costs to resolve the debt, such as legal consultation fees or court costs. Apart from that, NPLs can also affect the bank's reputation and reduce customer trust, which can reduce the amount of funds the bank receives from customers and affect BOPO.

(11) Return On Assets /ROA. ROA can influence BOPO in banking because ROA shows the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. If ROA is high, the bank can generate greater profits from the assets it owns, which can increase operational income and BOPO. However, if ROA is low, then the bank may not be able to generate sufficient profits from the assets it owns, which can affect BOPO.

(12) Return On Equity /ROE. ROE can influence BOPO in banking because ROE shows the bank's ability to generate profits from the capital it has. If ROE is high, the bank can generate greater profits from the capital it has, which can increase operational income and BOPO. However, if ROE is low, then the bank may not be able to generate sufficient profits from the capital it has, which can affect BOPO.

(13) Company size. Company size can influence BOPO in banking because larger banks tend to have more complex operations and greater operational costs. Additionally, larger banks may have more funds and resources to generate greater revenues, which can increase BOPO. However, smaller banks may have lower

operational costs and can be more flexible in adapting their business strategy, which may affect BOPO.

(14) Total assets. Total assets can also influence BOPO in banking because banks that have greater total assets may have better access to capital markets and greater resources to generate greater income. However, banks that have smaller total assets can be more flexible in adjusting their business strategies, which can affect BOPO.

V. Conclusion and Limitations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: Firstly, based on the mapping of the number of research publications regarding the ratio of Operational Costs to Operational Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2009 to 2023 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 736 journal publications. Second, based on VOSviewer mapping bibliometric studies, the network visualization results around the ratio BOPO in Sharia and Conventional Banking is divided into 4 clusters and 163 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 59 topics, cluster 2 consists of 55 topics, cluster 3 consists of 42 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 7 topics. Third, based on mapping studies Library Research, there are 49 topics related to the influence of the BOPO ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Audit Opinion, savings bonus, Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Debt to Asset Ratio / DAR, Fee Based Income, Financing to Deposit Ratio / FDR, Financial Distress, stock price, capital adequacy, zakat compliance, non-performing loans, credit quality, net profit, operating profit, liquidity, Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits, total assets, Allowance for Impairment Losses/CKPN, Murabahah margin, Market Share, Net Interest Margin /NIM, Net Profit Margin /NPM, Net Operating Margin /NOM, Non-Performing Loans /NPL, Non-Performing Financing /NPF, company value, return on assets, profit growth, changes in profits, lending, credit distribution, asset growth, Ijarah financing, Mudharabah financing, Price Earning Ratio /PER, Profit Distribution Management, bank rating, bond rating, Murabahah financing risk, Return On Assets / ROA, Return On Equity / ROE, stock returns, bank profitability, bank bankruptcy risk, Mudharabah savings, financial stability, and Tax Avoidance. And there are 14 topics related to the influence of BOPO ratios on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: productive assets, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Third Party Funds/TPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, inflation, non-performing loans, exchange rates/currency rates money, liquidity, Non Performing Financing /NPF, Non Performing Loans /NPL, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, company size, and total assets.

The limitation of this research is that the scope of the research only covers the influence and determinant variables of BOPO on Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2009 to 2022. The publications studied only come from the accredited national journal Sinta 1-6. These limitations mean that this research does not yet describe the effect of BOPO on banking as a whole. Apart from that, there are several international journals indexed by Scopus that have not been included in this research, whereas these journals are needed to compare the influence and determinants of BOPO on banking in Indonesia and other countries.

References

Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>

- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*

Islam, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik

- VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96.
<http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK

VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>

Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>

Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>

Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>

Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>

Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>